

Legal Analysis of Regional Leader Coordination Forums to Support the Implementation of Regional Government Duties and Functions by Government Regulation Number 12 of 2022 in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This investigation points to discovering out and analyze the lawful investigation of territorial authority coordination gatherings to bolster the usage of territorial government obligations and capacities in agreement with government control number 12 of 2022 in Indonesia, to discover out and analyze the supporting and repressing variables for the advancement of the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering organization. in supporting the usage of the obligations and capacities of regulating common government issues, to recognize and analyze endeavors to overcome the variables hindering the Organizational Advancement of the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering in supporting the execution of the obligations and capacities of regulating common government undertakings in Indonesia. This inquiry is a subjective inquiry about utilizing an inductive approach. The investigative strategies utilized are perception, documentation and interviews. Based on the results of the field examination, it can be concluded that there has been no improvement in the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering in Indonesia, but the usage of the obligations and capacities of regulating common government undertakings is still being carried out in a few locales. Within the advancement handle, the existing restraining components did not become an issue within the Organizational Improvement of the Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering in Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of territorial independence within the setting of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia has ended up more honed with critical accentuation in Law Number 23 of 2014. Another principal alter that's not contained in Law Number 32 of 2004 is the assurance of Obligatory Territorial Issues and the design of Concurrent Undertakings relations between Central, Common and Regency/City Governments, which are straightforwardly controlled within the Connection to Law Number 23 of 2014. This can be diverse from Law Number 32 of 2004 (Government Regulation Number 38 of 2007) which directs the relationship between the Central, Common and Territorial, which is displayed within the shape of Government Directions.

Within the classification of government undertakings, there are three sorts, to be specific outright government issues, concurrent government undertakings, and common government issues. Supreme government undertakings allude to the total specialist of the Central Government, whereas concurrent government undertakings include the division of specialists between the Central, Common and Regency/City Governments. Common government issues drop beneath the specialist of the President as head of government. (Nur Wijayanti 2017)

The sanctioning of Government Direction Number 12 of 2022 concerning territorial authority coordination gatherings, gives unused sees and streams within the territorial government framework in Indonesia. With the division of the organization of government issues into outright government, concurrent government and common government undertakings. In carrying out common government undertakings, these are things that drop beneath the specialist of the President as head of government, which are carried out by the Senator, Regent/Mayor helped by vertical offices as stipulated in Article 25 passage (3) of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Common government undertakings are government issues that incorporate the zones of peace and arrangement, legislative issues, coordination, supervision and other government undertakings which are not included within the obligations of an office and don't incorporate territorial family issues. Within the presence of Government Direction Number 12 of 2022 concerning Territorial Authority Coordination Gatherings, territorial government undertakings cannot be carried out autonomously, particularly things related to common government undertakings. Territorial governments require help from the Territorial People's Agent Board (DPRD), vertical offices and other related components. Hence, to carry out common government undertakings, a gathering was shaped which in Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Territorial Government is called the Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering or shortened as FORKOPIMDA. So, the gathering that joins together components of territorial authority already depicted in Law Number 5 of 1974 is called the Territorial Administration Conference (Muspida) changing its title to the Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering or truncated as FORKOPIMDA, where already in Law Number 22 of 1999 and

Law Number 32 of 2004 there was no unused gathering that seem to supplant the organization Territorial Administration Conference.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative methods, which are not much different from quantitative research in data collection techniques because qualitative research is also a type of field research approach, namely technology. ik total research data collection was carried out in the field.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The development of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum (FORKOPIMDA) organization to support the implementation of the tasks and functions of administering general government affairs in Indonesia can be seen from the system change model proposed by Kinicki and Kritner, as well as the vision and mission of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum (FORKOPIMDA).

The Regional Leadership Coordination Forum in each region follows the vision and mission of the regents and mayors which supports the implementation of general government affairs. Based on the vision and mission that has been prepared, a detailed strategic plan will be implemented regarding the vision and mission, aims and objectives, as well as the duties and functions of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum which will support the implementation of general government affairs. For implementation, the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum (FORKOPIMDA) and Regency/City Regional Leadership Coordination Forum (FORKOPIMDA) can invite heads of vertical institutions depending on the topic to be discussed. Legally, the role of the Regional Government Leadership Coordination Forum (FORKOPIMDA) is to discuss and implement general government affairs in its working area. General government affairs consist of seven types as regulated in Article 25 of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government.

1. To strengthen the practice of Pancasila, implement the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, preserve Binneka Tunggal Ika, as well as safeguard and maintain the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, national sharpness and increase national resilience.
2. Building national unity and integrity.
3. Encourage harmony between tribes, religions, races and other groups to achieve local, regional and national security stability.
4. Handle social conflicts by legal provisions.
5. Provincial and district/city governments resolve problems that arise by taking into account the principles of democracy, human rights, equality, justice, privileges and specialties, latent and regional diversity, provisions of laws and regulations, coordinating the implementation of tasks between authorities; and regulations - invitations.
6. Development of Democratic Life Based on Pancasila.
7. Implementation of all government affairs that are not within regional authority and are not implemented by vertical authority.

The development of FORKOPIMDA provides several elements that need to be adjusted, such as:

1. The Regional Leadership Coordination Forum does not yet have a policy or regulation to form a Regional Leadership Coordination Forum. The formation of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum will be discussed further and is in line with Government Regulation Number 12 of 2022 concerning the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum. Vision and Mission, Goals and Mission, Mission and Function, Membership, Work Relations, and Reporting and Finance,
2. Human resource development has not yet reached members of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum. The competency, knowledge and skills training carried out will be passed on to the sub-district head, which will be carried out directly by members of the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum.
3. Technology used in the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum methodology, coordination and communication processes. Technology can help you do your job more effectively and efficiently. Four).

The social factors present in holding the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum aim to establish good relations between members, establish harmonious communication and coordination, as well as build an organizational culture and good leadership from the leadership, namely the Regent. Participatory governance is a system in which public institutions directly involve non-state stakeholders in collective decision-making processes. This system is based on the principle of consensus, a deliberative approach, and has the aim of designing and implementing public policies, as well as managing public programs or assets. (Ansell and Gash 2008)

This definition emphasizes six primary criteria:

- (1) the gathering is started by an open body or institution,
- (2) gathering members include non-state on-screen characters,
- (3) members are specifically included in choice making, not fair "counseled" by the body's specialists open,
- (4) this gathering is held formally and accumulates collectively,
- (5) the point of the gathering is to reach choices through agreement (even though in hone agreement isn't continuously accomplished), and
- (6) the center of collaboration is centered on open approach or open administration.

This definition is more restricted than some definitions found within the writing. In any case, far-reaching utilization of the term, as Royal concedes, can impede the creating hypothesis (Majestic 2005, 286). Since we point to compare identical situations, we intentionally impose stricter imperatives on This is often to extend case closeness. (Ansell and Cut 2008)

The Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering is considered exceptionally great and can have a positive impact on all individuals who are

the administration components of their particular related components. Through the arrangement and advancement of the organization, it is trusted that the taking after comes about can be accomplished: At the organizational level, territorial authority coordination gatherings can be created. It is trusted that controls concerning territorial administration coordination gatherings can be defined in agreement with Government Control Number 12 concerning Territorial Administration Gathering Coordination. At the bunch, sector/group level of organizational advancement of the Indonesian Territorial Leadership Coordination Gathering, advancement happens within the shape of something that can be advertised by each administration component that's a portion of the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering to the community.

To realize great administration, it is necessary to apply common standards of great administration as a direct for government officials in utilizing specialists in issuing choices or controls. This rule points to supply a sense of security to the community. The open approach hypothesis isn't as it was related to the instrument of interpreting political choices into schedule methods through bureaucratic channels, but moreover includes perspectives of strife, choices, and the dispersion of approach comes about.

Large-scale or principal open arrangements incorporate the 1945 Structure, UU/Perpu, Government Controls, Presidential Controls, and Territorial Directions. Ensures equity must be reflected in each government arrangement, and for this reason, it is imperative to harmonize pertinent controls so that the open does not feel confounded and on edge around the rules that must be utilized as rules, to make legitimacy in acting.

The implementation of good governance is a fundamental requirement for every government to realize people's aspirations, achieve goals and achieve the country's aspirations. In this context, it is necessary to develop and implement an appropriate, clear and legal accountability system, so that governance and development can take place efficiently, successfully, cleanly and responsibly. (Surya and Wahab 2023)

Based on the explanation as intended in the paragraph, several challenges may be faced in enforcing the law against the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum, even though it is recognized as a good effort and can have a positive impact. Here are some challenges that can be identified:

1. Harmonization of Regulations: The law enforcement process can face challenges in harmonizing the regulations governing FORKOPIMDA at the organizational level. It is important to ensure that the coordination forum regulations comply with the provisions stipulated in Government Regulation Number 12 concerning Regional Leadership Forum Coordination.
2. Conformity with Legal Principles: Law enforcement requires firmness in ensuring that every action or policy produced by FORKOMPIMDA is by applicable legal principles, including human rights and constitutional provisions.
3. Community Empowerment: Other challenges may arise in community empowerment efforts through innovation offered by leadership elements in

FORKOMPIMDA. It is important to ensure that the innovation supports the interests and needs of society fairly and sustainably.

4. Inter-sectoral and Regional Coordination: FORKOPIMDA needs to face challenges in maintaining coordination and collaboration between sectors and regions. This can involve effective coordination to ensure the implementation of innovations in different regions according to local context and needs.
5. Monitoring and Evaluation: Challenges related to law enforcement in FORKOPIMDA also include effective monitoring and evaluation of forum activities. A strong mechanism is needed to ensure accountability and transparency in every action taken by the FKPD.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of law enforcement will depend largely on the extent to which the government and stakeholders involved can address these challenges systematically and proactively.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The advancement of the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering (FORKOPIMDA) organization in supporting the execution of the errands and capacities of regulating common government issues in locales in Indonesia can be seen from the altered framework demonstrate that the vision and mission of the Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering in Districts in Indonesia takes after the vision and mission from the nearby Official and Leader in supporting the usage of common government issues. From the vision and mission that has been made, it is at that point deliberately arranged in detail concerning the vision and mission, points and targets, as well as the obligations and capacities of the territorial administration coordination gathering to back the usage of common government undertakings. Indeed even though advancement does not show up to be fast within the Territorial Administration Coordination Gathering organization in Indonesia, the usage of the obligations and capacities of regulating common government undertakings is still being carried out. Within the improvement handle, the existing inhibiting variables did not end up an issue within the advancement of the Territorial Authority Coordination Gathering organization within the locales in Indonesia.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Legal Analysis of Regional Leader Coordination Forums to Support the Implementation of Regional Government Duties and Functions by Government Regulation Number 12 of 2022 in Indonesia".

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